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HOMESCHOOLING UNDER DEBATE IN BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze how the legal advance of Homeschooling in Brazil takes place. The hypothesis is that the discussion about Homeschooling is part of an ongoing political-ideological plan in the country. A bibliographic review was carried out based on specialized academic literature published in the last four years. Through a bibliographical review, it was concluded that the Homeschooling theme is complex and carries an ideological background that highlights an idea of educational dismantling in progress in the country.